

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI) 2024

The 20th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations ([AIAI](#)) was held from 27 – 30 June in a Hybrid format, in Corfu and online. **AIAI is a renowned international conference that brings together scientists and researchers** each year to exchange the latest and most cutting-edge advances in the field. Its programme includes workshops that provide an ideal setting for the presentation of leading-edge conference papers.

DATAMITE had a strong presence at this year's conference. On the one hand, DATAMITE organised and moderated a panel discussion with other EU-funded

projects, and, on the other hand, the project presented **five conference papers in two different sessions**: 5G-PINE 2: 5G – Putting Intelligence to the Network Edge (5G-PINE) Workshop, and CSAD (Cyber Security / Anomaly Detection) session.

[Read the full article](#)

International events

International Supercomputing High Performance Event

The [International Supercomputing \(ISC\) High Performance 2024](#), was held from 12 – 16 May in Hamburg, Germany. **DATAMITE**, of course, did not want to miss the event, and **was represented by Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC)**, a member of the consortium.

[Discover more](#)

DATAMITE at Data Week 2024

The [second part of Data Week 2024](#) took place in Leuven (Belgium) on 5 June. Under the theme *Data Value Unlocked*, 11 sessions were held, including “Data Value creation”, in which **DATAMITE participated**. This session discussed relevant aspects to take into account when obtaining high value from data. **Daniel Sáez Domingo**, Technology Transfer Director [ITI](#), attended on behalf of **DATAMITE** to participate in the experts discussion, held during the second part of the debate.

[Discover more](#)

DATAMITE returns to Field Days

The [National Field Days](#), the largest industry event in Poland, took place from 7 to 8 June 2024. After the [success of last year's edition](#), **DATAMITE has participated again** thanks to two of the consortium members: the Wielkopolska Agricultural Advisory Centre in Poznan ([WODR](#)) and the Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center ([PSNC](#)).

[Discover more](#)

Campaign: Meet the people behind DATAMITE

DATAMITE is an ambitious project with a consortium of 26 organisations from 12 countries, but beyond the numbers are the people. **With the series "Meet the people behind DATAMITE"** we want to introduce the people who work

every day to achieve our ambitious goal: to deliver a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve data monetising, interoperability, trading and exchange in the form of software modules, training and business materials for European companies, empowering them to become new relevant players in the data economy.

Mariano Blaya Andreu (IDSA)

We present **Mariano Blaya Andreu**, Director of Delivery at International Data Spaces Association ([IDSA](#)). “At the beginning of the DATAMITE project I helped/led the preparation of, what we call, the state-of-the-art involving the data spaces and the building blocks, also using the knowledge coming from IDSA, but also from Data Spaces Support Centre ([DSSC](#))”, he explain.

When asked what makes DATAMITE special, Mariano states that ” the DATAMITE framework is going to play a critical role on helping the participants from the different aspects: from the quality point of view, from the monetization point of view, and from the connectivity. **The DATAMITE framework is going to ease the onboarding** and the connection of different sectors”

[Watch his interview](#)

Summer reading

Must-read summer reading

It is July and that means holidays are just around the corner! Disconnection from the daily routine and all the time in the world to rest and do one of the things we love the most: reading. As **there is no summer without reading**, we propose **five articles for you to get to know DATAMITE better** and come back with your batteries recharged. Happy summer break and happy reading!

- **How have we contributed to the EU year of Skills?** 2023 was the European Year of Skills. The main objective of this year was to help businesses, in particular small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), to address the skills shortage in the EU. **DATAMITE**, well aware of the need to improve the digital skills of society, **contributes to improve skills in technical and business aspects** thanks to the multiple open source training materials that the project is generating and will generate. Read it [here](#).
- **DATAMITE and the development of common EU data spaces.** the European Commission has established the European data strategy. A roadmap to make the EU leader in the **new data-driven society, creating a single market for data** to pool European data in key sectors, with common and interoperable data spaces. One of DATAMITE's objectives is to support the deployment of these Common European Data Spaces, thanks to its relevant partners in the International Data Spaces (IDS) ecosystem. Find out how we plan to do this by reading the article [here](#).
- **Use Cases.** Our use cases are the heart of DATAMITE. They are the key to testing, improving and validating our modular, open-source, multi-domain framework for improving data monetisation. We **present three of them** in depth:
 - **Corporate Multi-Site Data exchange**. Discover it [here](#).
 - **Connecting eDWIN to data markets**. Discover it [here](#).
 - **Offering Data to service Providers with DataSpaces**. Discover it [here](#).

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